

15 **Abstract**

16 Drifting buoy observations of ocean surface waves in hurricanes are combined with mod-
 17 eled surface wind speeds. The observations include targeted aerial deployments into Hur-
 18 ricane Ian (2022) and opportunistic measurements from the Sofar Ocean Spotter global
 19 network in Hurricane Fiona (2022). Analysis focuses on the slope of the waves, as quan-
 20 tified by the spectral mean square slope. At low-to-moderate wind speeds ($< 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$),
 21 slopes increase linearly with wind speed. At higher winds ($> 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), slopes continue
 22 to increase, but at a reduced rate. At extreme winds ($> 30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), slopes asymptote. The
 23 mean square slopes are directly related to the wave spectral shapes, which are charac-
 24 terized by an equilibrium tail (f^{-4}) at moderate winds and a saturation tail (f^{-5}) at
 25 higher winds. The asymptotic behavior of wave slope as a function of wind speed could
 26 contribute to the reduction of surface drag at high wind speeds.

27 **Plain Language Summary**

28 Drifting buoy observations of ocean surface waves in Hurricanes Ian and Fiona (2022)
 29 are combined with modeled wind speed to explore the evolution of the sea surface from
 30 moderate to extreme winds (up to 54 m s^{-1}). The sea surface is characterized using the
 31 physical slope of the waves, or the ratio of a wave's height to its length, which has pre-
 32 viously only been well-understood up to moderate wind speeds of 15 to 20 m s^{-1} . At lower
 33 wind speeds, the average slopes increase proportional to the wind speed, meaning the
 34 waves continually steepen as the wind strengthens. At higher winds, the slopes continue
 35 to increase, but at a reduced rate. The slopes eventually reach a maximum value at the
 36 most extreme winds (i.e., the slopes saturate). This phenomenon is accompanied by a
 37 change in sea surface character from one that is patterned by occasional wave breaking
 38 to one that is almost entirely covered by whitecaps and foam. Using wave slope as a mea-
 39 sure of the roughness of the ocean surface, the observed wave slope saturation could help
 40 to explain the relative reduction in wind surface forcing at extreme wind speeds.

41 **1 Introduction**

42 The physical slope of ocean surface waves, defined as the ratio of a wave's height
 43 to its length (H/L) or product of its amplitude and wavenumber (ak), is widely found
 44 to play a governing role in the exchange of momentum at the air-sea interface. Slope is
 45 essential in the parameterization of deep-water breaking processes (Duncan, 1981; Melville,

1994; Drazen et al., 2008; Schwendeman et al., 2014; Schwendeman & Thomson, 2017, and others) and is theorized to contribute to the air-sea drag coefficient through modulation of the aerodynamic roughness (Taylor & Yelland, 2001; Troitskaya et al., 2012; Takagaki et al., 2012, 2016; Donelan, 2018; Lan et al., 2022). Efforts to characterize slope as a function of wind speed trace back to Cox and Munk (1954), who used optical measurements of the sun’s glint to measure the distribution of slopes in wind speeds ranging from 1 to 14 m s⁻¹. This work was followed by an extensive set of satellite radiometer measurements reported by Bréon and Henriot (2006) up to 12 m s⁻¹, the airborne lidar-based measurements of Lenain et al. (2019) from 2 to 13 m s⁻¹, and most recently, the spaceborne measurements of Guérin et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2022). These works universally agree that, in low-to-moderate winds, the mean square of the slope distribution, or *mean square slope*, increases linearly with wind speed. Dynamics above 20 m s⁻¹ remain less thoroughly investigated.

The mean square slope (mss) is a metric that quantifies the average steepness of waves over a range of frequencies or wavenumbers. When estimated from the wave energy density spectrum, it is an integral quantity proportional to the fourth moment of the spectrum. It can be calculated across any portion (or the entirety) of the spectrum, and it is closely related to the shape of the spectrum itself. Typically, an actively forced, wind-driven gravity wave spectrum has a single peak followed by a broad spectral “tail”. The canonical tail of a wind-driven gravity wave spectrum has two distinct regions: an *equilibrium range* and a *saturation range* (Forristall, 1981; Banner, 1990; Lenain & Melville, 2017). The *equilibrium range* is defined by a balance of wind input, dissipation from breaking, and nonlinear energy fluxes. It begins just beyond the peak frequency and is characterized by a distinct f^{-4} spectral slope in frequency, or $k^{-5/2}$ in wavenumber space (Toba, 1973; Phillips, 1985). At frequencies beyond the equilibrium range, a *saturation range* exists, where the wind input is balanced by dissipation from breaking (Forristall, 1981; Banner, 1990; Romero et al., 2012; Lenain & Melville, 2017). This region is characterized by a spectral slope of f^{-5} (k^{-3} in wavenumber space).

Wave slope and spectral shape, particularly the tail, are closely tied to the wind forcing. Through the use of a Phillips (1985) analytical expression for spectral energy in the equilibrium range related to mean square slope, Thomson et al. (2013) demonstrated the feasibility of estimating wind stress based on wave spectral observations alone. In that work, the equilibrium-derived estimates of wind speed compare well with observed

79 wind speeds up to 15 m s^{-1} , enabling operational use of the method to derive proxy wind
 80 speeds in the Sofar Spotter global network (Voermans et al., 2020). However, at higher
 81 wind speeds, the dependence of *mss* and the evolution of wave spectral shape remains
 82 largely unexplored, except in models (Donelan, 2018) and in the laboratory (Takagaki
 83 et al., 2012, 2016).

84 Previous studies of ocean surface waves in high winds under hurricanes and extra-
 85 tropical cyclones have focused on wave evolution and general surface conditions (Holthuijsen
 86 et al., 2012; S. A. Hsu et al., 2017; Walsh et al., 2021; Kita & Waseda, 2022). Waves evolve
 87 rapidly in hurricanes, especially in fast-moving storms under which the effective fetch
 88 and duration of forcing changes with storm translation speed (Kudryavtsev et al., 2015;
 89 Hwang, 2016; Hwang & Fan, 2017; J.-Y. Hsu et al., 2019; Hell et al., 2021). Wave di-
 90 rections vary dramatically based on location relative to the center of the storm, with large
 91 wind-wave misalignment possible in the left quadrants (Walsh et al., 2002; Young, 2006;
 92 Hwang & Walsh, 2018; Collins et al., 2018; Tamizi & Young, 2020; J.-Y. Hsu, 2021). The
 93 interaction of waves and currents can also be significant (Yujuan et al., 2018; Hegermiller
 94 et al., 2019; Bruciaferri et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2022). This literature has lacked an ob-
 95 served relation between wave slopes and wind speeds in hurricanes that can be used to
 96 improve models (Janssen & Bidlot, 2023).

97 Here, we use buoy spectral measurements in hurricane winds to study the evolu-
 98 tion of wave slope and spectral shape as a function of modeled wind speed. Section 2
 99 describes the determination of *mss* from the buoys and describes the coupled model used
 100 for surface wind speeds. Section 3 presents the results, and Section 4 discusses the im-
 101 plications and relation to other studies. Section 5 concludes.

102 **2 Methods**

103 **2.1 Mean square slope definition**

104 An estimate of the wave mean square slope can be computed from a frequency spec-
 105 trum as (Ticona Rollano et al., 2019, for example),

$$106 \quad \text{mss} = \int \frac{(2\pi f)^4 E(f)}{g^2} df = \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} \frac{(2\pi f)^4 E(f)}{g^2} df \quad (1)$$

107 Here a , k , and f represent the wave amplitude, wavenumber, and frequency, $E(f)$
 108 is the energy density, and g is the acceleration of gravity. The indefinite integral is di-
 109 rectly proportional to slope squared (a^2k^2) using the linear dispersion relationship in the
 110 deep water limit, $(2\pi f)^2 = gk$, and with $E(f) \propto a^2$. The definite integral represents
 111 an estimate of the mean square slope over a frequency extent defined by its minimum
 112 and maximum frequencies, f_{\min} and f_{\max} . Here, the limits are taken as the lowest and
 113 highest reported frequencies of the spectrum resolvable by the finite-sized wave buoy, $f_{\min} =$
 114 0.0293 Hz to $f_{\max} = 0.5$ Hz in $n = 33$ discrete bands, where the upper limit is set by
 115 the hydrodynamic response of the hull. We emphasize that this mean square slope met-
 116 ric characterizes the shape and slope contributions of the energetic gravity wave range
 117 of the spectrum, but cannot account for waves shorter than approximately 6.3 m in wave-
 118 length (see section 4.1).

119 2.2 Spotter wave buoy

120 Wave measurements were collected by free-drifting Spotter buoys (Sofar Ocean)
 121 which use GPS-derived motions to report hourly records of surface wave statistics in the
 122 form of scalar energy spectra and directional moments (Raghukumar et al., 2019). Raw
 123 data are collected at 2.5 Hz over an 1800 s period and processed using 102.4 s windows
 124 with 50% overlap to produce spectral estimates spanning 0.0293 Hz to 0.5 Hz in 33 bins.
 125 The sphere-like hull is 42 cm in diameter with a mass of 7.5 kg including ballast.

126 2.3 COAMPS-TC model

127 Surface wind field estimates are derived from real-time operational forecasts made
 128 by the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory’s (NRL) Coupled Ocean-Atmosphere Mesoscale
 129 Prediction System for Tropical Cyclones (COAMPS-TC) (Doyle et al., 2012, 2014). COAMPS-
 130 TC is a regional model which uses an outer fixed grid mesh (36-km horizontal resolu-
 131 tion) and two nested storm-following grid meshes (12- and 4-km resolution) with 40 ver-
 132 tical levels ranging in altitude from 10 m above the surface to approximately 30 km. When
 133 producing real-time operational forecasts, the version of COAMPS-TC used in this study
 134 utilizes the NOAA Global Forecast System (GFS) analysis and forecasts for the initial
 135 and boundary conditions. For storms that have intensities greater or equal to 55 knots
 136 (28.3 m s^{-1}), the horizontal wind structure at the initial time of the model is generated
 137 from a modified Rankine wind vortex model combined with both physical and synthetic

Figure 1. Buoy locations and storm track for Hurricane Ian (left) and Hurricane Fiona (right). Storm tracks are colored by intensity, as categorized by the Saffir-Simpson scale, and the surrounding wind swaths are shaded by wind speed threshold. The insets highlight several buoy-storm interactions using 10-m wind speeds from COAMPS-TC.

138 observations ingested from the National Hurricane Center. For time periods when the
 139 storm intensity is less than 55 knots at the initialization time, the initial TC vortex is
 140 downscaled from the NOAA GFS analysis.

141 Hourly 10-m winds from the inner-most 4-km grid are derived by aggregating suc-
 142 cessive forecasts leaving out the first four hours of each forecast to minimize the effect
 143 of model state adjustments that occur early in each forecast. The winds are interpolated
 144 onto Spotter wave observations to produce wind-wave datasets in Hurricanes Fiona and
 145 Ian (2022).

146 **2.4 Targeted deployment measurements in Hurricane Ian (2022)**

147 Hurricane Ian was a Category 4 hurricane that caused widespread damage to both
 148 Cuba and the Southeastern United States during late September 2022. Ahead of Ian’s
 149 first U.S. landfall on the Southwest coast of Florida, the continental shelf was seeded with
 150 an array of drifting buoys in a targeted deployment by an NP-3C aircraft (Figure 1) op-
 151 erated by Naval squadron VXS-1. Observations from six Spotter buoys in the array are
 152 co-located with wind fields from COAMPS-TC to create a dataset of 432 hourly wave
 153 measurements and modeled wind speeds from September 27 to 30, 2022. Wave obser-
 154 vations span 2 m to 11.8 m significant wave height and 5 s to 13 s peak period, and lie

155 between the 30 m and 100 m depth contours, approximately 90 km to 275 km offshore.
 156 The maximum COAMPS-TC wind speed at the time and location of a Spotter obser-
 157 vation is 52.5 m s^{-1} (117 mph).

158 **2.5 Sofar Spotter Network measurements in Hurricane Fiona (2022)**

159 Hurricane Fiona was a destructive hurricane that formed in mid-September 2022
 160 and made landfall in Puerto Rico and the Dominican Republic before traveling North-
 161 ward across the Atlantic, peaking in intensity as a Category 4, then striking Eastern Canada
 162 as an extratropical cyclone. Fiona’s track through the open Atlantic intersected with sev-
 163 eral buoys in Sofar’s Spotter network – a large, persistent-array of free-drifting Spotter
 164 buoys (Houghton et al., 2021). The 3167 hourly observations from 33 Spotters (Figure
 165 1) contain measurements up to 17.5 m significant wave height and 20.5 s peak period,
 166 with a maximum interpolated model wind speed of 54.4 m s^{-1} (122 mph).

167 **3 Results**

168 **3.1 Mean square slope versus wind speed**

169 At low-to-moderate wind speeds ($< 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), observed mean square slopes have
 170 a linear dependence on 10-m surface-level wind speed (Figure 2). This result is quali-
 171 tatively consistent with the measurements of Cox and Munk (1954) at wind speeds of
 172 2-14 m s^{-1} .

173 At higher wind speeds ($> 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), the increases in observed mss are much smaller.
 174 This trend persists through the extent of available buoy data, up to the maximum wind
 175 speed of 54.4 m s^{-1} (122 mph) as modeled by COAMPS-TC. An empirical hyperbolic
 176 tangent fit to the buoy mss observations is shown in Figure 2 as

$$177 \text{mss}_{\text{fit}}(U_{10}) = a \tanh(bU_{10}) - c, \quad U_{10} \in [2, 55] \text{ m s}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

178 With coefficients $a=0.020 \pm 0.0002$, $b=0.057 \pm 0.0009 \text{ s m}^{-1}$, $c=-0.0017 \pm 0.0.0001$ and
 179 a root mean square error of 0.0016 when fit to the entirety of the data ($n=3599$ hourly
 180 observations). The data are fit using the SciPy Python library curve fit routine (non-
 181 linear least squares) and the parameter variance is computed from the diagonal of the
 182 estimated covariance matrix. The tanh fit is linear (to within 5%) up to a wind speed

Figure 2. Spotter mean square slope from wave measurements in Hurricanes Ian and Fiona as a function of COAMPS-TC 10-m wind speed. An empirical $a \tanh(b U_{10}) - c$ fit is shown with coefficients $a=0.020$, $b=0.057$, and $c=0.0017$.

183 of 14.5 m s^{-1} , which is in good agreement with the original Cox and Munk results and
 184 the literature that follows.

185 In wind-wave flume experiments, Troitskaya et al. (2012) found wave slope to have
 186 a similar tendency toward saturation which was coincident with saturation of the lab-
 187 oratory air-sea drag coefficient above wind speeds of 25 m s^{-1} . The authors attribute the
 188 decrease in slope to the “tearing of the wave crests at severe wind conditions.” In the
 189 University of Miami Wave Model, there is a similar transition in mean square slopes at
 190 high winds, though the values do not fully saturate Donelan (2018). A more complete
 191 comparison with other mss results from the literature is given in the discussion (Sec 4.1).

192 **3.2 Spectral shape change with wind speed**

193 Mean square slope is a measure of both the physical wave slope ($a^2 k^2$) as well the
 194 wave spectral shape (i.e., as the fourth moment of the spectrum). The evolution of the
 195 observed wave spectra with wind speed is shown in Figure 3 as the mean energy den-
 196 sity in 10 m s^{-1} bins. At low-to-moderate wind speeds ($< 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), the spectral tail above

Figure 3. *Upper panel:* mean energy density in 10 m s⁻¹ bins. Bin counts are labeled inside of the color bar (a count is a spectrum observed over a 1-hour period). *Lower panel:* the mean energy spectra compensated by f^4 (as $energy \cdot f^4$) and normalized by their respective maximum value. In such a scaling, f^{-4} trends collapse to a constant line (as indicated by the correspondingly labeled dashed line).

197 0.10 Hz follows the canonical f^{-4} slope expected of the equilibrium range (wind input,
 198 dissipation from breaking, and nonlinear energy fluxes in balance).

199 From 15 to 25 m s⁻¹, the equilibrium range is shorter and the tail of the spectrum,
 200 from 0.2 Hz onward, transitions to the f^{-5} slope characteristic of the saturation range
 201 (wind input balanced solely by dissipation). This change is coincident with the weak-
 202 ening of the wind speed dependence of mss in Figure 2; thus mss is integrated over spec-
 203 tral energy decaying as f^{-4} at lower wind speeds, and mss is integrated over a saturated
 204 tail with energy decaying as f^{-5} at higher winds. The equilibrium range (f^{-4}) narrows
 205 with increasing wind speed, until the spectral tail is almost entirely dominated by the

206 saturation range (f^{-5}) at the most extreme winds (45 to 55 m s⁻¹). For any given to-
 207 tal wave energy (or significant wave height), the change in spectra shape to f^{-5} results
 208 in a reduction in mss, relative to an f^{-4} shape with the same total energy. Thus, wave
 209 heights can continue to increase with increasing wind speed, while mss saturates.

210 While observational evidence of slope and spectral tail saturation at extreme wind
 211 speeds is scarce, several works have highlighted trends in low-to-moderate wind speeds
 212 (< 20 m s⁻¹). Ticona Rollano et al. (2019) observed wave slope saturation with wind
 213 speed starting at wind speeds of 11 m s⁻¹ and noted the saturation to be qualitatively
 214 similar to the saturation of measured turbulent dissipation in the ocean surface layer.
 215 Observations of the transition from the equilibrium to saturation subrange by Vincent
 216 et al. (2019) and Lenain and Melville (2017) demonstrate the transition frequency (and
 217 wavenumber) decreases with increasing wind speed (in wind speeds up to 20 m s⁻¹). While
 218 neither result extends to the extreme, 55 m s⁻¹ wind speeds observed here, the transi-
 219 tion frequency appears to decay exponentially with an apparent asymptote at 0.30 Hz
 220 in the Vincent et al. (2019) data (max winds 20 m s⁻¹).

221 Spectra with a narrow equilibrium range and dominant f^{-5} saturation slope are
 222 present in the SWIFT buoy observations of Schwendeman et al. (2014). The authors note
 223 the SWIFT spectra derive from young, highly forced waves (which is the case here) as
 224 defined by the wave age, or the ratio of wave phase speed to the 10-m wind speed. This
 225 trend is in agreement with the results of Romero and Melville (2010) that demonstrate
 226 a narrowing of the equilibrium range and increase in saturation with decreasing wave age.
 227 Spotter spectra, binned by wave age, are shown in the supplement (Figure S1) and are
 228 consistent with this wave age dependence.

229 **4 Discussion**

230 **4.1 Limitations of wave scales observed by buoys**

231 It is well known that buoys cannot measure waves shorter than a few meters be-
 232 cause the hydrodynamic response of their hull is limited to frequencies longer than the
 233 natural frequency (typically 0.5-1.0 Hz, see Thomson et al. (2015) for details). This limi-
 234 tation creates a known bias in buoy-based estimates of the integral mss, relative to other
 235 methods such as lidar (Lenain et al., 2019) and polarimetry (Zappa et al., 2008). Lenain
 236 and Melville (2017) used lidar measurements to demonstrate that the saturation and cap-

237 illary ranges contribute a substantial portion of the mean square slope in data with wind
 238 speeds up to 11 m s^{-1} and significant wave heights from 0.8 to 2.5 m. This bias is par-
 239 tially corrected by incorporating empirical parameters into (1) which effectively extrap-
 240 olate the spectra to higher frequencies,

$$241 \quad \text{adjusted mss} = \alpha \int_{f_{\min}}^{f_{\max}} \frac{(2\pi f)^4 E(f)}{g^2} df + \beta. \quad (3)$$

242 The empirical factors α and β are introduced to account for the mean square slope con-
 243 tributions of the higher frequency waves not resolvable by the Spotter buoy (i.e., waves
 244 shorter than $f_{\max} = 0.5 \text{ Hz}$ or 6.3 m in wavelength). Fitting α in Equation (3) to Cox
 245 and Munk (1954) over the linear regime of Figure 4 (from 2 to 15 m s^{-1}) yields $\alpha = 5.3$
 246 with an offset of $\beta=0.01$.

247 In Figure 4, adjusted mss (with $\alpha=5.3$ and $\beta=0.01$) is compared to the data of Cox
 248 and Munk as well as the slopes modeled by Donelan (2018) using the University of Mi-
 249 ami Wave Model. The Miami wave model includes the full spectrum of gravity, capillary-
 250 gravity and capillary waves in prescribing mss. In this same figure, equation (2) is shown,
 251 refit with coefficients $a=0.109 \pm 0.0009$ and $b=0.057 \pm 0.0007 \text{ s m}^{-1}$ and a root mean
 252 square error of 0.0086. (The offset, c , is no longer needed.) In all datasets, the transi-
 253 tion to a regime with weaker mss dependence on wind speed is observed near 15 m s^{-1} ,
 254 corresponding to an approximate slope of 0.08 or $\tan(16 \text{ deg})^2$ as identified by Cox and
 255 Munk (1954). The adjusted mss and Donelan results are in good agreement up to a wind
 256 speed of 30 m s^{-1} . Beyond that, the Donelan model results exceed the Hurricane Ian and
 257 Fiona observations by 15 to 30%. At high winds ($> 30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), the model exhibits a sen-
 258 sitivity to fetch (which is beyond the scope of the present study). Interestingly, the ad-
 259 justed buoy mss in Figure 4 appear capped by the upper limit on omnidirectional mean
 260 square slope proposed by Plant (1982), $\text{mss}_{\max} = 0.08 \pm 0.04$, or using the upper value,
 261 $\text{mss}_{\max} = 0.12$. The limit is proposed based on requirement that the flux of momen-
 262 tum from wind to waves should not exceed the wind stress for wave growth proportional
 263 to $(u^*/c)^2$, and is employed by Elfouhaily et al. (1997) to vet several candidates for para-
 264 metric spectra.

265 While useful for a rough comparison of buoy mss to slopes calculated over larger
 266 frequency extents, there remains large uncertainty in the use of α and β to correct buoy
 267 mss to total mss. The coefficient α is biased when the transition from the equilibrium
 268 range to the saturation range (Figure 3) is well within the frequencies resolvable by the

Figure 4. Adjusted mean square slope, calculated from Equation (3) with $\alpha=5.3$ and $\beta=0.01$ using wave measurements in Hurricanes Ian and Fiona, as a function of model 10-m wind speed. An $a \tanh(bU_{10})$ fit is shown with $a=0.109$ and $b=0.057$. The classic field measurements of Cox and Munk (1954) are superimposed along with the University of Miami Wave Model slope estimates at fetches of 4 km and 230 km from Donelan (2018).

269 buoy, which occurs around wind speeds of 15 to 20 m s^{-1} , since the contribution to mss
 270 of a saturated portion of the spectrum is less significant than that of an equilibrium por-
 271 tion of the spectrum (or similarly higher-sloped portion). This coefficient is also sensi-
 272 tive to the evolution of the wave spectrum in the gravity-capillary range (wavelengths
 273 less than 1 m down to several millimeters) which changes shape with increasing wind speed
 274 (Elfouhaily et al., 1997; Munk, 2009).

275 In future work, the NOAA Wide Swath Radar Altimeter (WSRA) and Stepped Fre-
 276 quency Microwave Radiometer (SFMR) instruments are good candidates for producing
 277 relevant datasets of hurricane winds and waves (Walsh et al., 2021; Klotz & Uhlhorn,
 278 2014). The WSRA measures wave topography (which can be used to compute mss) and
 279 SFMR provides a measure of surface wind speed. Both fly concurrently aboard the NOAA
 280 WP-3D aircraft during Hurricane Hunter missions.

4.2 Implications for surface drag coefficient

The air-sea drag coefficient, which governs the rate of momentum transfer between the air and ocean surface, depends on the surface roughness length under neutral stability (Charnock, 1955). Taylor and Yelland (2001) demonstrated the ability of a roughness length scaling based on wave slope (H/L) in the gravity wave range to predict observed roughness across a wide range of datasets, including the open ocean. Similarly, Takagaki et al. (2012) found an H/L roughness dependence in the lab. Using a groundbreaking set of GPS sonde tropical cyclone field measurements, Powell et al. (2003) observed a saturation in both roughness length and drag coefficient (followed by Holthuijsen et al. (2012)). While a direct connection to of mss to drag is beyond the scope of this paper, it follows that the present observation of wave slope saturation in hurricanes could be a plausible mechanism for the sea-state dependent reduction in roughness length, and as such, a reduction in drag coefficient at hurricane force wind speeds.

The underlying processes that are related to mss and may modulate the drag coefficient include: intense wave breaking (Hwang, 2018), wave sheltering (Kudryavtsev & Makin, 2007; Donelan, 2018, and others), and the increasing presence of foam and spray above 30 m s^{-1} (Holthuijsen et al., 2012; Troitskaya et al., 2016, 2019, and others). Recently, Lan et al. (2022) achieved notable tropical cyclone model skill improvement through the use of a roughness parameterization that depends both on sea state and foam, employing the Taylor and Yelland (2001) slope scaling at low wave ages (<15.2) and the Drennan et al. (2003) wave age scaling at higher wave ages. Donelan (2018) takes a more direct approach and uses the mean square slope to motivate the increase in flow separation as waves steepen. Though a mean square slope integrated up to high frequencies might be necessary for a direct relation to the skin friction component of the drag coefficient, the slope of the waves in the gravity range measured by buoys remains important to the understanding of form drag and pressure work. The buoy measurements, though lacking the very highest frequency waves, include the vast majority of the total energy in the wave spectrum. More practically, the buoy measurements are the wave information most readily available for real-time assimilation into coupled forecast models.

4.3 Secondary dependencies of mss at high winds

Although this set of buoy data has been sufficient to determine a parametric relation between mss and wind speed, it has not been sufficient to determine secondary dependencies. Building on ideas from the literature, we have tested the residual scatter from the tanh fit in Figure 2 for dependence on storm quadrant (position relative to the center and heading of the storm), wind-wave alignment, wave age, and storm speed. While none of these tests show a statistically significant result, there are some possible signals. When viewing the time series of each individual buoy rather than the aggregated data, the mss values are higher for a given wind speed when the winds and waves are well-aligned. The alignment dependence would be consistent with formulations for wind-wave growth that utilize the wind stress vector and the wave celerity vector (Gemrich et al., 1994). Time series figures are included in the Supplemental Material.

5 Conclusions

Ocean surface wave buoy measurements within two hurricanes show a consistent regime change in the relation of wave slopes to wind speeds. Up to moderate wind speeds ($< 15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), wave slopes increase linearly with wind speed, as has been documented in the literature. At higher wind speeds, wave slopes appear to reach an upper limit, with no further increase beyond 30 m s^{-1} winds. The upper limit is similar a heuristic value of 0.12 proposed by Plant (1982). This mss limit is directly related to the emergence of an f^{-5} saturation range as the dominant shape of the scalar wave energy spectra under high wind speeds. The wave slope changes are likely related to changes in the surface drag coefficient, for which a more comprehensive dataset is needed to evaluate. A larger dataset of wave observations in more hurricanes will be valuable for considering secondary effects, such as dependencies on storm quadrant, wind-wave alignment, the interaction between swell and wind-sea, and storm speed.

Open Research

Please note the data is currently archived on Dryad as “Private for peer review.” The data can be accessed at the temporary link: <https://datadryad.org/stash/share/q3IhGvRkLZd3XB8eFB0eFZ606KzI7vGiXV-LdF2pKZk>. The following is written using the appropriate DOI which will be available for use following peer review.

340 The wind and wave data used in this work are publicly available at Dryad via [https://](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g4f4qrfvb)
341 doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g4f4qrfvb (Davis et al., 2023). The storm track and speed
342 data used to test secondary dependencies were sourced from IBTrACS (Knapp et al., 2010,
343 2018). Shapefiles of the storm track and wind swaths used in the maps are from the Na-
344 tional Hurricane Center GIS Archive available at <https://www.nhc.noaa.gov/gis/>.

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Supporting Information for “Saturation of ocean surface wave slopes observed during hurricanes”

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Contents of this file

1. Figures S1 to S10.

Introduction

In Figure S1, Spotter spectra are shown as mean energy density binned by wave age. With decreasing wave age, the equilibrium range continually narrows until it is almost nonexistent at wave ages as low as 0.3 to 0.4.

Figure S2 shows the sensitivity of Spotter mean square slope coefficients α and β to frequency extent defined by f_{\min} and f_{\max} . For a constant minimum frequency at the lower end of the gravity range, $f_{\min}=0.05$ Hz, the mean square slope is calculated by integrating

the fourth moment up to each upper frequency limit, f_{\max} . Each set of Spotter mean square slope data is then fit to the measurements of Cox and Munk (1954) over the linear mean square slope region (2 to 15 m s⁻¹). Using the coefficients of each linear fit, the mean square slope coefficients α and β which adjust the Spotter data to the fully-resolved Cox and Munk (CM) data are calculated as:

$$\alpha = m_{\text{CM}}/m_{\text{Spotter}} \qquad \beta = C_{\text{CM}} - \alpha C_{\text{Spotter}} \qquad (1)$$

where m and C are the slope and intercept of each respective fit over 2 to 15 m s⁻¹.

Figures S3-S6 show Spotter-hurricane time series in Ian and Fiona. Here time series of COAMPS-TC wind speed and mean square slope are compared with wave age, wind-wave misalignment, buoy position in the storm, and storm speed. Wind-wave misalignment is calculated as $\text{mod}(\theta_{\text{wind}} - \theta_{\text{wave}} + 180, 360) - 180$ to retrieve the smallest of the two possible angles resulting from the difference $\theta_{\text{wind}} - \theta_{\text{wave}}$. Regions corresponding to following, crossing, and opposing wind and swell, as defined by Holthuijsen et al. (2012), are indicated on the plot. Position in the storm is referenced to the storm heading and is calculated as the relative bearing from the storm center to the buoy's position. Storm track, heading, and speed are obtained from the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS) (see Knapp et al. 2010 and 2018 in the main document).

Figures S7 and S8 show the mean square slope data versus wave age and inverse wave age. Figures S9 and S10 are the same but for the adjusted mean square slope values.

Figure S1. *Upper panel:* mean energy density binned by wave age (bin counts labeled inside color bar). The wave age is calculated as the ratio of the wave phase speed, at the mean period, to the 10-m wind speed. Bin resolution is increased at low wave ages to highlight the behavior of young seas. *Lower panel:* the mean energy spectra compensated by f^4 (as $energy \cdot f^4$) and normalized by their maximum value.

Figure S2. Sensitivity of Spotter mean square slope coefficients α and β to frequency extent when fit to the measurements of Cox and Munk (1954).

Figure S3. Spotter-Ian time series. In the topmost image, the hurricane and Spotter buoy are shown at the mean time. Their trajectories are shown as a grey line with a black arrow (hurricane path and direction) and as black dots (hourly buoy positions). The red ‘x’ indicates the end of the buoy’s trajectory. Where applicable, metrics derived from both the peak and mean periods are indicated as black dots and green squares, respectively.

Figure S4. Spotter-Fiona time series no. 1 (same description as in Figure S3).

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Figure S5. Spotter-Fiona time series no. 2 (same description as in Figure S3).

Figure S6. Spotter-Fiona time series no. 3 (same description as in Figure S3).

Figure S7. Spotter mean square slope versus mean period wave age.

Figure S8. Spotter mean square slope versus mean period inverse wave age.

Figure S9. Adjusted mean square slope versus mean period wave age.

Figure S10. Adjusted mean square slope versus mean period inverse wave age.